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Effect Of Interest Rate Reforms On Private Sector Investment In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the effect of interest rate reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria for the period of 1987 to 2021. The objective of the study was to examine the effect of: monetary policy rate, liquidity rate, cash reserve and money supply on private sector investment in Nigeria. The variables were private sector investment as the dependent variables while monetary policy rate, liquidity rate, cash reserve and money supply, were the independent variables. These variables were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria bulletin. Secondary type of data were utilized in this study, the population of the study was deposit money banks listed on the Nigeria Exchange Limited, The Autoregressive Distributive Lag approach was employed for the analysis The study found a positive and significant effects from cash reserve (0.1689, $p = 0.0049$), on private sector investment. The coefficient for Liquidity ratio (-0.0159, $p = 0.0049$) has a negative and significant effect on private sector investment. Nonetheless, monetary policy rate (0.0004, $p = 0.2524$) and money supply (0.9458, $p = 0.0689$) showed positive coefficient with probability value greater than 0.05 level of significance. The study concludes that interest rate policy instruments play an important role in shaping private sector investment in Nigeria, their effectiveness varies across instruments. Coordinated and carefully managed monetary policies are therefore essential for promoting sustained private sector investment. The study recommend that, The Central Bank of Nigeria should strengthen the interest rate transmission mechanism by addressing high lending spreads, improving financial intermediation, and promoting competitive pricing of credit in the banking system. Monetary authorities should adopt a more flexible liquidity framework that allows banks to extend adequate credit to productive sectors without compromising financial stability. CRR should be deployed strategically to maintain banking sector stability while ensuring that sufficient funds are channeled to private sector investment, particularly to small and medium-scale enterprises.

Keywords: Monetary policy rate, liquidity rate, cash reserve and money supply,, private sector investment

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Interest rate policy is a fundamental monetary policy instrument used by governments and central banks to influence investment, savings, and overall economic activity. In Nigeria, interest rate reforms have been implemented as part of broader financial sector reforms aimed at improving the efficiency of the

financial system, enhancing credit allocation, and stimulating private sector-led economic growth (Uwakwe, 2025). The private sector, regarded as the engine of economic development, depends heavily on access to affordable and stable credit, making interest rate policy particularly important for investment decisions. Private sector investment is critical for employment generation, industrial development, technological advancement, and sustainable economic growth. In Nigeria, however, investment by the private sector has often been constrained by high cost of borrowing (Dike, Okeke, Eboh and Ezeibe 2025), limited access to long-term finance, and macroeconomic instability. High interest rates increase the cost of capital, reduce expected returns on investment, and discourage firms from undertaking new investment projects or expanding existing ones. Small and medium-scale enterprises, which form the backbone of the Nigerian private sector, are particularly affected due to their limited access to alternative sources of finance (Isiaka, 2022).

Theoretically, interest rate reforms are expected to positively influence private sector investment by improving savings mobilization and increasing the availability of loanable funds. However, excessively high or unstable interest rates can have the opposite effect by discouraging borrowing and investment (Naftaly, & Edwin, 2024).. Empirical studies on the relationship between interest rate reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria have produced mixed results, with some findings suggesting a negative effect of high interest rates on investment, while others argue that liberalization improves financial intermediation and investment in the long run. Given the persistent challenges of high lending rates and subdued private sector investment in Nigeria (Nguyen 2024), it is important to empirically examine the effect of interest rate reforms on private sector investment. This study therefore seeks to assess how changes in interest rate policy have influenced private sector investment in Nigeria, with a view to providing evidence-based recommendations that can support the design of interest rate policies conducive to private sector-driven economic growth.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Interest rate reforms were introduced in Nigeria to enhance financial sector efficiency, improve credit allocation, and stimulate private sector investment through market-determined interest rates. However, despite these reforms, lending rates in Nigeria have remained persistently high and volatile, raising concerns about their effectiveness in promoting private sector investment. The high cost of borrowing has constrained private sector access to credit, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises that rely heavily on bank financing for investment and expansion. Instead of stimulating investment, interest rate reforms appear to have increased financial burdens on investors, thereby discouraging long-term private sector investment. Furthermore, frequent monetary policy adjustments and macroeconomic instability have created uncertainty in the financial market, making it difficult for private investors to plan and undertake sustainable investment projects. Empirical evidence on the relationship between interest rate reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria also remains mixed and inconclusive. These challenges raise the question of whether interest rate reforms have effectively achieved their intended objective of stimulating private sector investment in Nigeria, thereby necessitating an empirical investigation into their actual impact.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to ascertain the effect of interest rate reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. investigate the effect of monetary policy rate on private sector investment in Nigeria;
2. examine the effect of liquidity rate on private sector investment in Nigeria;
3. ascertain the effect of cash reserve on private sector investment in Nigeria;
4. investigate the effect of money supply on private sector investment in Nigeria;

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Interest rate Reforms

Interest rate is the cost of borrowing money by the borrower. It is also return to the depositor in his/ her account in bank, or return on investments such as government bonds. It is the channel through which the funds flow from savers to borrower. Usually these funds are generated from financial intermediaries like scheduled banks, development banks, mutual funds and insurance companies etc. It is an indicator that determines the flow of funds from savers to borrowers directly, or through financial intermediation. If the supply of loanable fund is more than the demand of loanable fund, interest rate falls, and if the demand is more than the supply, interest rate rises. Fluctuation in interest rate and changes in the quantity of loanable funds affect the economic indicators such as economic growth, level of income, general level of prices and investment (Aftab, Jebran, Ullah & Awais, 2016).

Interest Rate and Monetary Policy Reforms are among the reforms that started with the Deregulation of interest rate in the year 1987, and in 1989. It brought about the introduction of the auction market for government securities which was also introduced as well as the continued use of other direct monetary policy instruments (cash reserve requirements). In 1990, stabilization securities for liquidity management was introduced, and in 1991 interest rate controls was reintroduced with the removal of interest rate controls i.e. Liberalization of bank credit market in 1992. And lastly, the Introduction of indirect monetary instruments (open market operations), Re-imposition of interest controls as part of review of the Central Bank operations, Continuation of interest controls Initiated fiscal reforms, and Retention of interest controls as well as Continuation of fiscal reforms all took place in 1993, 1994, 1995 and 1996 respectively (Omankhanlen, 2012). The goal of interest rate reform is to achieve efficiency in the financial sector and engendering financial deepening. Nnanna and Dogo (1998) viewed financial deepening as a financial system which is largely free from financial repression. Under such a liberalized system, the market should determine the behaviour of lenders and borrowers (Obamuyi, & Demehin, 2012).

2.1.2 Private Sector Investment

The economy of every country has two broad participants which are the private sector and the public sector. The private sector is the part of a country's economic system that is run by individuals and companies, rather than a government entity. Investment by most private sector organizations are done with the intention of making profit.

In Keynesian terminology, investment refers to addition to capital equipment which enables an increase in the production of capital goods (Jhingan, 2002). The term, investment, according to Ibenta (2005), may be defined as accumulation and commitment of fund in financial and real assets with the objective of obtaining income over time. He further noted that it is a commitment of resources made in the hope of realising benefits that are expected to occur over a reasonably long period of time in the future. Investment can also be referred to as the production of capital goods (Heim, 2008). Investment thus includes new plant and equipment, construction of public works like roads, dams, buildings, etc. Investment can be defined as the outlay of money for future use (Agu, 2015).

Investment can be made by the corporate organisation for individual stakeholders or directly by the individual in a certain project. This is known as Private Investment. But, when the commitment of funds for productive purposes is done by the government for the betterment of the citizenry, it is called Public Investment.

Private sector investment in Nigeria is faced with some daunting challenges. For decades, Nigeria's economy was characterized by growing dominance of the public sector over the private sector. The private sector faced numerous problems which include; the poor state of physical infrastructure, particularly road networks, electricity and water supply; inadequate credit to the private sector, which has dove-tailed to high cost of production; insecurity in the country; corruption at various levels; weak institutions, etc. (Okorie&Chikwendu, 2019).

The private sector plays a vital role in the economy by creating jobs, providing goods and services, and stimulating economic growth. The private sector is a key driver of innovation. As a result of this, private

companies invest in research and development, which leads to new products and services that boost the economy, improve lives and tremendously enhance competitions with great revenues generated.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Keynesian Theory

The theory was propounded by John Maynard Keynes, a British Economist in February 1936. This theory postulates that interest rate is determined by the demand and supply of money. He maintains that the rate of interest is purely a monetary phenomenon and as such, distinct from the real theory of the Classics. Keynes notes that savings and investment refer to the aggregate savings and aggregate investment. Investment means production that is not currently consumed which may take the form of machinery, equipment, building, etc while savings is the amount of current income which is not spent upon consumption, (Soyibo and Adekanye, 1992). Keynes further notes that the determinants of interest rate will be found in the money market and that they are basically the supply and demand for money (Christopher 2022). He identified three motives for the desire to hold cash; transactionary motive, precautionary motive, and speculative motive but noted that transactionary and precautionary motives are influenced by the level of income while speculative motive is influenced by the level of interest rate (<https://www.unn.edu.ng/>). He reveals that if there is no interest receivable, people would hold their assets in the form of cash, so to get people to hold their wealth in other forms apart from cash, one must receive interest (Inimino, Abuo, and Bosco, 2018).

2.3 Theoretical Exposition

Interest Rate Reform and Private Investment Hypothesis

The global financial crisis of 2008/2009 re-ignited the debate around the growth effects of interest rate reforms. Authorities worldwide reduced interest rates to low levels in an attempt to boost aggregate demand and economic growth. Lower interest rates are also purported to increase investment levels by reducing borrowing costs. The recovery from the global financial crisis has been slow despite the lowering of interest rates as investments and economic growth rates continue to be at low levels in most parts of the world. According to the advocates of the Austrian school, like Kates (2010) and Templeman (2012), maintaining low interest rates during a crisis slows the recovery process (Moyo & Le Roux, 2018).

The pioneers of the financial liberalization hypothesis, McKinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) argued that financial reforms promote economic growth by encouraging savings and investments. Therefore, policies that keep interest rates at artificially low levels may have a negative impact on savings and investments which are one of the major determinants of long-term economic growth as suggested by growth models of Harrod (1948), Domar (1948), Solow (1956), Swan (1956) and Romer (1986). Critics of the financial liberalisation hypothesis suggest that savings may not be responsive to higher interest rates and the rise in borrowing costs caused by interest rate reforms have a negative effect on investments (see Warman & Thirwall, 1994; De Melo & Tybout, 1986).

In the 1970's, some economists, led by McKinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973), began to argue in favour of financial liberalization as a medium of promoting saving, investment, and growth. This was based on the argument that real interest rates are frequently negative in developing countries due to administrative controls on the nominal interest rates and heavy regulation in the financial market. This argument implies that real interest rates have a net positive effect on private investment, contradicting the traditional view of a negative relationship between private investment and real interest rates. Nevertheless, the financial liberalization literature argues in favour of higher interest rates due to what was observed in developing economies at the time, and the possibility of a negative relationship between investment and interest rates was not ruled out. McKinnon (1973) argued that in those countries where self-finance is very important and the interest rate is negative or very low, an upward increase in real deposit rates encourages saving (the substitution effect dominates the income effect) and the substitution from goods to bank deposits. Both have positive effects on private investment because self-financed investment rises and because there is a rise in the availability of funds to finance any profitable investment project. However, at higher rates, economic agents would prefer to hold deposits that yield a higher return than investment in physical

capital. Therefore, at high rates, investment and real bank rates are expected to be negatively related. Hence, McKinnon's arguments imply a nonlinear relationship between real interest rates and private investment.

The main argument of McKinnon- Shaw (1973) was that an increase in the real interest rate may induce savers to save, which generates more investment. Therefore, the expectation of interest rate reform was to encourage domestic savings and make great loanable funds available in the banking system. However, the "tunnel-like" structure of interest rates (Ojo, 1976) in Nigeria was capable of discouraging savings and retarding growth in view of the link between savings, investment and economic growth (Obamuyi & Demehin, 2012).

2.4 Empirical Studies

Moyo and Le Roux (2018) examine the effect of interest rate reforms on economic growth through savings and investments in SADC countries for the period 1990-2015. Three specifications are used for the analysis; the first one determines the influence of interest rate reforms on savings, the second one analyses the effect of savings on investments while the third one examines whether investments have a positive impact on economic growth. In the core model, investment was the dependent variable, followed by savings, (GDP less consumption expenditure), real interest rate, domestic credit to the private sector and foreign direct investments net inflows as the independent variable. The Pooled Mean Group (PMG) estimation technique is employed for analysis. Also, the ARDL bounds tests were carried out for the individual countries to test for cointegration. The results show that cointegration is detected in most countries for each one of the three specifications. Also, interest rate reforms have a positive impact on economic growth through savings and investments.

Aftab, Jebran, Ullah and Awais (2016) examined the long- and short-term effect of interest rate on private sector credit on Pakistan for a period of 1975 to 2011. This study applied Auto Regressive Distribution Lag (ARDL) model for the data analysis. The results revealed significant negative effect of interest rate on private sector credit in the long run, and also in the short run. The results also indicated significant positive effect of inflation on private sector credit in long and short run. However, exchange rate was found to have no effect on private sector credit.

Obamuyi and Demehin (2012) employed the cointegration and vector error correction models (VECM) to investigate the effect of interest rate reforms on financial deepening in Nigeria with the period covering 1973 to 2009. The study regressed the financial deepening variable (M2/GDP) on the nominal deposit rate (NDR), inflation rate (IFR), the lagged value of financial depth (M2/GDP_{t-1}), growth rate of gross domestic product (GRG), domestic savings/GDP ratio (SAV), exchange rate (EHR), liquidity reserve ratio (LRR) and shift in financial policy from regulation to deregulation of interest (FPS). The results indicate that there exists a long run relationship between financial deepening and interest rates. The study further revealed that interest rate reform has a positive and significant effect on financial deepening in Nigeria.

Bader and Malawi (2010) examined the effect of interest rate on private investment in Jordan, by using cointegration analysis. The results indicated that investment was negatively affected by real interest rate. The results highlighted that one percent increase in the rate of interest reduced the investment by 44 percent, while income level affects investment positively.

Orji, Egbirenmolen and Ogbuabor (2014) investigated the effect of interest rate reforms on investment in Nigeria. The study found that the real interest rate and savings have a positive impact on investments in Nigeria.

Ajayi (2014) examined the effect of financial sector reform and monetary policy on Nigeria economy for a period from 1980 to 2012. The study employed econometric technique by regressing Credit allocation to Private Sector, Liquidity Ratio and Interest Rate on Gross Domestic Product. It was found that all variables truly affected Gross Domestic Product both in the short and long-run. The causality test shows that only Credit Allocation to Private Sector and Interest Rate caused Gross Domestic Product while the other variable is caused by Gross Domestic Product. The study concludes that the reform measures were

not inherently defective and that the management of the reform process skillfully would go a long-way in achieving the goals of the monetary and fiscal authorities and the country at large.

Utilie, Okwori and Ikpambese (2018) investigated the effect of interest rate on the economic growth of the Nigerian economy. The aim of the study was to determine the effect of inflation rate, exchange rate and deposit interest rates on the gross domestic product of the country. The data for the study was obtained from the statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria from 1980-2016. The research design adopted for the study was the *ex-post facto*. Multiple regression technique was used for the analysis of data. The student t-test was used to test the hypotheses formulated. It was found that INF and EXR have negative and insignificant effect on GDP. Also it was found that DIR has positive and significant relationship with GDP. The study concludes that interest rate has a negative and insignificant relationship with GDP.

Ajayi, Oladipo, and Nwanj (2017) assessed the effect of interest rate on Economic Growth of Nigeria. The study adopted an Error-Correction Mechanism to test for the short - and long – run relationships among the savings’ deposit, real interest rate and inflation, ECM is negative and further test of Granger causality indicates that there is a causal relationship between SD and GDP and a unidirectional relationship exists between SD and GDP. Therefore, Savings’ deposit causes Gross domestic product. The study recommends that policies which would boost the savings’ accumulation in Nigeria that will increase Capital Formation are necessary for economic growth. This will also enhance lending to the real sector of the economy for productive economic activities. This could be done by increasing the deposit rate which would lure people to deposit their money in the banks thereby increasing the supply of loanable funds.

Maiga (2017) examined the effects of interest rate on economic growth in Gambia over the period 1993 to 2017. The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) is used to check the relationships between the dependent variable (Gross Domestic Product) and independent variables (Real Effective Exchange Rate and Real Interest Rate), both in the short-run and long-run. Post estimation tests, including Lagrange Multiplier test for residual autocorrelation were also conducted for autocorrelation, as well as Jarque Bera to test for stability and to check whether residuals are normally distributed. The empirical evidence indicates that there is no short-run association between the growth of the Gambian economy and interest rate but that there is a long run connection that runs from real interest rate and real exchange rate to GDP.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The *ex-post facto* research design was employed in this study. This design is suitable for secondary data studies, especially when the data has already been documented and authenticated by some great research based institutions like the World Bank, IMF, CBN among others (Kerlinger, 1973). It is a well-known fact that in this regression study, the researcher investigated a cause and effect relationship without manipulating the existing data.

3.2 Nature and Sources of Data

The study used secondary data which are collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria publications. The data covered a period of thirty five (35) years (1987 to 2021). This period covered the post Structural Adjustment Programme era.

3.3 Model Specification

The objective of this study was addressed in this model. The model is premised on the assumption that interest rate influences private sector investment. The functional model is as shown below:

$$PI = f(MPR, LR, CR, MS) \text{-----Model 1}$$

Where:

PI = private sector investment

MPR = Monetary policy rate

LR = Liquidity rate

CR = Cash reserve
 MS = Money supply

This can be rewritten in equation form as follows:

$$PI = d_0 + d_1MPR + d_2LR + d_3CR + d_4MS + \mu \text{-----Eqn 2}$$

d_0 is the autonomous value of the constant while d_{1-4} are the coefficients of the independent variables. The μ is the error term that smoothen the stochastic effect of time series' disturbances on the model.

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

This study adopts econometric techniques in testing the effect of interest rate on private sector investment. It employs time series data necessitates stationarity tests in order to avoid spurious results. The unit root test is expected to determine the nature of the time series data and the most suitable tool of regression technique to employ. It is expected that in cases where all the variables are stationary at level (1(0)), the Ordinary Least Square tends to be the most suitable regression technique, whereas the Johansson cointegration works better in situation where all the variables take the forms of first order integration 1(1). In cases where the econometric variables have a combination of both level 1(0) and first integration 1(1), the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) works best.

3.5 A priori Expectation

The a priori expectation in each of the models is as follows: $\beta > 0$; this explains the theoretical linkage on the sign and magnitude of parameter of the specified functions. The Sign (>) indicates an improvement on Private Sector Investment as the dependent variable. This supposes that increase in any variable in the interest rate reform paradigm increases by a unit.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1 Unit Root Test

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests was employed to determine the stationarity or otherwise of variables used in the study. The ADF tests are done on level series, and first order difference series. The decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, otherwise, accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value.

Table 1: Summary of Unit Root Test for Stationarity

Variables	At Level 1(0)		At First Difference 1(1)		Order of Integration
	T-stat	P.Value	T-stat	P.value	
Private Sector Investment (PI)	-3.929579	0.0056	-	-	1(0)
Money supply (MS)	-2.113713	0.2408	-5.502564	0.0001	1(1)
Monetary policy rate (MPR)	-3.0196	0.0444	-	-	1(0)
Liquidity rate (LR)	-8.262101	0.0062	-	-	1(0)
Cash reserve (CR)	-1.6622	0.4362	-4.265321	0.0031	1(1)

The stationarity test otherwise called unit root analysis shows that some of the variables are stationary at level {that is had no unit root at 1(0)} while others were not stationary at level but become stationary in their first differences {that is, they had no unit roots at 1(1)}.

The variables with the order of integration of 1(0) are PI, MPR, and LR,. Since the decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, and accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value at level, thus we rejected the null hypothesis as the p.values are less then 0,05 and conclude that each of them is stationary at level 1(0).

Those that have the order of integration of 1(1) are MS, and CR Since the decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, and accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value, the p.values of the ADF of each of these variables is greater than the 5% critical value at level but less than 0.05 at their first difference. Therefore, all the variables are all stationary at either level 1(0) or first difference 1(1).

4.2 Estimation of Long run Effect of interest rate on Private Sector Investment

The test of cointegration for the presence of a long-run relationship in the models is shown in Table 2. The ARDL result was used to compare the bound critical values with the F-statistics values. The decision rule: If the F-statistic is above the upper and lower critical bound values, then there is a long run relationship in the model; but where the F-statistics is below the upper and lower bound critical values, it is inferred that there is no long-run effect (relationship). The null hypothesis is that “No long-run relationship exists”.

Table 2: ARDL Bounds Test for long run effect of interest rate on private sector investment

Models	F-Statistic	Lower Critical Value Bound at 5% level	Upper Critical Value Bound at 5% level
Interest Rate Reforms	18.9790*	2.45	3.61

*significant at 5%

From the results in Table 2, the critical bound values were computed at 5% level of significance. The lower critical bound value is 2.45 while the upper critical value is 3.61. The F-statistics for the models is 18.9790. The F-statistics for all the models are greater than the Upper (3.61) and Lower (2.45) critical bound values. Thus we rejected the null hypotheses for all the models and conclude presence of long run relationship in all the models.

4.3 Analyses of ARDL Long Run Coefficients and Error Correction

Having established the presence of long-run relationships in interest rate and private sector investment in Nigeria, this section explained the nature of the relationship as well as the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium. The results from CointEq (-1) from the cointegrating form is used to explain the speed of adjustment. The nature of the relationship is explained by the long run coefficients.

4.3.1 Analyses of Long Run Effects of Interest Rate Reform on Private Sector Investment

Table 3: Model of the long run relationship between interest rate reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(PI(-1))	1.228996	0.214416	5.731825	0.0012
D(PI(-2))	0.334733	0.263974	1.268055	0.2518
D(MPR)	-0.007126	0.001726	-4.128990	0.0062
D(MPR(-1))	0.000191	0.001335	0.143285	0.8908
D(MPR(-2))	-0.012379	0.001784	-6.940056	0.0004
D(LR)	-0.040442	0.007196	-5.619801	0.0014
D(LR(-1))	0.037621	0.007405	5.080196	0.0023
D(LR(-2))	-0.030888	0.005126	-6.025344	0.0009
D(CR)	0.077779	0.025629	3.034760	0.0230
D(CR(-1))	-0.074526	0.033286	-2.238978	0.0664
D(CR(-2))	-0.177198	0.038467	-4.606494	0.0037
D(MS)	-0.327837	1.721519	-0.190435	0.8552
D(MS(-1))	-0.575923	0.837623	-0.687567	0.5174
CointEq(-1)	-2.892377	0.336136	-8.604770	0.0001

Cointeq = PI - (0.0004*MPR - 0.0159*LR + 0.1690*CR + 0.9458*MS + 0.0466)

Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.

MPR	0.000434	0.000343	1.266059	0.2524
LR	-0.015860	0.003652	-4.343044	0.0049
CR	0.168952	0.023593	7.161173	0.0004
MS	0.945818	0.427521	2.212332	0.0689
C	0.046597	0.320679	0.145307	0.8892

The nature of long run relationship and significance of the interest rate reform model is shown on Table 3. The error correction of -2.8923 was rightly signed with a negative coefficient to indicate that any deviation from normalcy has the tendency to return to equilibrium in due time. The probability value of 0.0001 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Thus the study rejects the null hypothesis of no long run adjustment to equilibrium. This indicates that interest rate reforms have a significant long-run effect on the private sector investment in Nigeria.

The long run cointegrating equation drawn from the long-run coefficients of regression on Table 3 revealed a positive and significant effects from cash reserve (0.1689, $p = 0.0049$), on private sector investment. This means that a unit increase in cash reserve, increases private investment in proportion of 16%. However, the coefficient for Liquidity ratio (-0.0159, $p = 0.0049$) has a negative and significant effect on private sector investment. Nonetheless, monetary policy rate (0.0004, $p = 0.2524$) and money supply (0.9458, $p = 0.0689$) showed positive coefficient with probability value greater than 0.05 level of significance.

4.3.2 Short run Effect of Interest Rate Reform on Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Table 4: Short Run Model of the Relationship between Interest Rate Reform and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
PI(-1)	-0.663381	0.212390	-3.123410	0.0205
PI(-2)	-0.894263	0.220107	-4.062863	0.0066
PI(-3)	-0.334733	0.263974	-1.268055	0.2518
MPS	-0.007126	0.001726	-4.128990	0.0062
MPS(-1)	-0.003807	0.001867	-2.038664	0.0876
MPS(-2)	-0.000191	0.001335	-0.143285	0.8908
MPS(-3)	0.012379	0.001784	6.940056	0.0004
LR	-0.040442	0.007196	-5.619801	0.0014
LR(-1)	0.001301	0.004681	0.277976	0.7904
LR(-2)	-0.037621	0.007405	-5.080196	0.0023
LR(-3)	0.030888	0.005126	6.025344	0.0009
CR	0.077779	0.025629	3.034760	0.0230
CR(-1)	0.159170	0.042863	3.713462	0.0099
CR(-2)	0.074526	0.033286	2.238978	0.0664
CR(-3)	0.177198	0.038467	4.606494	0.0037
MS	-0.327837	1.721519	-0.190435	0.8552
MS(-1)	2.487578	1.371403	1.813892	0.1196
MS(-2)	0.575923	0.837623	0.687567	0.5174
C	0.134776	0.928793	0.145108	0.8894
R-squared	0.998357			
Adjusted R-squared	0.991786			
F-statistic	151.9222			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000002			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.684661			

The analysis of the endogenous effect of the dependent variable (Private Sector Investment) on the model revealed that PI had negative and significant effects after the first and second years. This means that a growth in private sector investment is expected to lead to subsequent year fall in private investment in the next two years.

The coefficient of monetary policy rate (MPR) showed a negative (-0.0071) and significant (0.0062) short-run effects in the initial year, but a positive (0.0124) and significant (0.0004) short-run effect after the third year. This portends a sporadic effect of monetary policy on private investment in the economy. However, liquidity ratio had no statistically significant coefficients within the short run periods. Nonetheless, the short run effect of the cash reserve showed a positive (0.0265) and significant (0.0013) after the third year. Other prior years from the initial to the lag 2 indicated negative relationships with no significant effects. More to this is that cash reserve showed positive effect at all the short run periods, and statistically significant at initial year, lag 1 and 3, respectively. This suffices to say that cash reserve has a significant positive short-run effect on private investment in Nigeria.

On the contrary, money supply showed no significant effect on private sector investment in Nigeria. The coefficients for the periods are negative in the initial period (-0.3278) and positive at lag 1 (2.4875) and lag 2 (0.5759) respectively; with all having p.values greater than 0.05 level of significance.

On the overall, the adjusted coefficient of determination ($Adj R^2$) revealed that about 99% of the change in private sector investment (PI) can be explained by monetary policy reform instruments in Nigeria. This is confirmed by a statistically significant p.value of 0.0000 from the F-statistics (151.92). The Durbin-Watson statistics of 2.68 suggests a suspicion on the confounding influence of trends on the reliability of the model.

4.5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Interest rate reform instruments have long run and short run significant effects on private sector investment in Nigeria. Interest rate reform through the instrumentality of monetary policy impacts on private sector investment. This is true both in the short and long run periods. Besides, the outcome is in agreement with the a priori expectation and theoretical framework of Mckinnon-shaw (1973). In the long run, private sector investment would be impacted by a negative drive from liquidity ratio (-0.0158, $p = 0.0049$) and positive effect from cash reserve (0.1689, $p = 0.0004$). This means that a reduction in liquidity ratio and increase in cash reserve ratio is expected to boost private sector investment in the long run. This supposes that Nigeria can achieve long run improvement in private sector investment if the monetary policy stance pursues a reduced liquidity and increased cash reserve for the banks in Nigeria.

More so, all the price based monetary policy instruments like the monetary policy rate (MPR), liquidity ratio (LR), cash reserve (CR) have interloping short run effects on the private sector investment in Nigeria. For instance, MPR had a negative effect at initial period (-0.0071, $p = 0.0062$) and then positive effect at the lag 3 (0.0123, $p = 0.0004$) within the short run period on private sector investment. In the case of the LR, it was negative at initial period (-0.0404, $p = 0.0014$) and lag 2 (-0.0376, $p = 0.0023$), and then positive effect at lag 3 (0.0308, $p = 0.0009$); whereas the effect was positive for CR from the initial period (0.0777, $p = 0.023$) through the lag 2 (0.1591, $p = 0.009$) and lag 3 (0.1771, $p = 0.0037$) periods.

The specific findings of the study are that monetary policy rate have negative effect in the long run but intermittent of positive and negative influences through the short run; whereas cash reverse consistently holds positive effect on private investment. The liquidity ratio only has effect on the short run such that it reduces private investment. These findings are unique at the instant of previous studies. For instance, findings from the works of Ulilie *et al* (2018); Ajayi *et al* (2017); Orji *et al* (2014); Obamuyi & Demihin (2012) and Ajayi (2014) from Nigeria have significant positive effect on the national economy and private sector investment. Extant results from previous studies such as Moyo & Le Roux (2018) covering Angola, Democratic Republic of Congo, Mozambique and Zimbabwe as well as Maiga (2017) from Gambia strongly agree with the above findings. Whereas Mifta (2019); Aftab *et al* (2016) as well as Barde & Malawi (2010) from Nigeria contradicted them.

5.1 CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of interest rate related monetary policy instruments on private sector investment in Nigeria, using the monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio, cash reserve ratio, and money supply as key explanatory variables. The empirical findings reveal that the monetary policy rate (MPR) exerts a positive but statistically insignificant effect on private sector investment. This suggests that changes in the policy rate alone have not been sufficient to meaningfully influence investment decisions, possibly due to weak policy transmission mechanisms, high lending rates, and structural inefficiencies within the financial system.

The liquidity ratio was found to have a significant negative effect on private sector investment, indicating that higher liquidity requirements reduce banks' capacity to extend credit to the private sector. This contraction in credit availability discourages investment, particularly in capital-intensive and long-term projects.

In contrast, the cash reserve ratio (CRR) exhibited a significant positive relationship with private sector investment. This implies that prudent reserve management enhances financial stability and investor confidence, thereby supporting increased investment activities. A stable banking environment appears to encourage the flow of funds to the private sector.

Furthermore, money supply showed a significant positive effect on private sector investment, affirming that increased liquidity in the economy improves access to credit and reduces financing constraints faced by private investors. This highlights the importance of adequate monetary expansion in stimulating private sector-driven growth.

Overall, the findings indicate that while interest rate policy instruments play an important role in shaping private sector investment in Nigeria, their effectiveness varies across instruments. Coordinated and carefully managed monetary policies are therefore essential for promoting sustained private sector investment.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

- i. The Central Bank of Nigeria should strengthen the interest rate transmission mechanism by addressing high lending spreads, improving financial intermediation, and promoting competitive pricing of credit in the
- ii. Monetary authorities should adopt a more flexible liquidity framework that allows banks to extend adequate credit to productive sectors without compromising financial stability.
- iii. CRR should be deployed strategically to maintain banking sector stability while ensuring that sufficient funds are channeled to private sector investment, particularly to small and medium-scale enterprises.
- iv. The Central Bank should pursue controlled expansionary monetary policies aimed at increasing credit availability while keeping inflationary pressures in check.
- v. There is a need for effective coordination among interest rate policy instruments and continuous monitoring of their impact on private sector investment to ensure that monetary policy objectives align with Nigeria's growth and development goals.

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